

are thankful to Dr. Y. D. Kulkarni of Lucknow University for making the screening results available.

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Synthesis of 3-t-Butylimino-4-aryl/alkyl-5-aryl/alkylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines and their De-t-butylolation into related 3-Imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines

N. K. KHANDELWAL, B. N. BERAD
and

M. G. PARANJPE*

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur-440 010

Manuscript received 19 February 1986, revised 8 July 1986,
accepted 22 April 1987

RECENTLY, we have reported the synthesis of 3,5-diarylimino-4-aryl-1,2,4-dithiazolidines involving the interaction of *N*-aryl-*S*-chloroisoithiocarbamoyl chloride and 1,3-diarylthiocarbamides¹. In this communication, we report the synthesis of certain *t*-butyl group containing 1,2,4-dithiazolidines and their debutylolation with the help of concentrated hydrobromic acid and a mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid and hydrochloric acid (1 : 3).

Interaction of *N*-*tert*-butyl-*S*-chloroisoithiocarbamoyl chloride (1) and 1,3-di-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide (2a) was carried out in cold benzene medium for 36 h. During the reaction the evolution of hydrogen chloride was observed. After the removal of unreacted 2a, the filtrate was evaporated and the resultant semi-solid mass was triturated several times with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) to give a pale yellow solid, crystallised from benzene, m.p. 162°. The product was found to be non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. On thermal decomposition, smells of *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate and *tert*-butyl isothiocyanate were clearly detected. On reaction with boiling

alcoholic ammonical hydrogen sulphide of moderate concentration, it afforded 2a. On reaction with benzylamine in boiling ethanolic medium, 1-*p*-tolyl-3-benzylthiocarbamide, m.p. 124° and 1-*t*-butyl-3-benzylthiocarbamide, m.p. 96° were isolated. On reaction with ethanolic picric acid, a picrate, m.p. 183° was isolated. The infrared spectra of the product clearly indicated the presence of $\nu_{C=N}$ (1 580), ν_{C-S} (650), ν_{S-S} (560) and a band at 1 370 cm^{-1} due to *tert*-butyl group^{2,3}.

On the basis of all the above facts, the product with m.p. 162° has been assigned structure 3-*t*-butylimino-4-*p*-tolyl-5-*p*-tolylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (3a).

The reaction of 1 was found capable of extension to other 1,3-diaryl/alkyl-thiocarbamides (2b–e) and the corresponding 3b–e were isolated. However, 3b and 3c were isolated as solid hydrochlorides and crystallised from glacial acetic acid (Table 1).

TABLE 1—3-*t*-BUTYLIMINO-4-ARYL/ALKYLIMINO-1,2,4-DITHIAZOLIDINES (3)

Sl. no.	2 (g)	3 (Yield%)	M.p. °C	Analysis% :		Eq. wt.
				Found/(Calcd.)	N	
1.	2a (11.5)	3a (95.8)	162	10.85 (11.38)	16.89 (17.80)	—
2.	2b (10.0)	3b HCl (48.2)	141	11.05 (11.14)	16.18 (16.70)	380.0 (877.5)
3.	2c (11.0)	3c HCl (48.7)	226	10.42 (10.37)	15.18 (15.80)	409.0 (405.5)
4.	2d (10.0)	3d (51.5)	148	11.18 (11.38)	16.48 (17.91)	—
5.	2e (12.0)	3e (46.0)	147	10.75 (11.38)	16.95 (17.31)	—

* C, H analyses satisfactory in all cases.

To product 3a when refluxed with concentrated hydrobromic acid for 3 h went into solution with the evolution of *tert*-butyl bromide. The resultant clear solution on cooling afforded a new product, m.p. 253°. It was non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. On thermal decomposition, it gave the smell of *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate. When treated with ethanolic picric acid, it afforded a picrate⁴, m.p. 230°. The ir spectra of the product clearly indicated the presence of ν_{NH} (3 450), $\nu_{C=N}$ (1 650), ν_{C-N} (1 280) and ν_{C-S}

TABLE 2—FORMATION OF HYDROBROMIDES OF 3-IMINO-4-ARYL/ALKYL-5-ARYL/ALKYLLIMINO-1,2,4-DITHIAZOLIDINES (4)

Sl. no.	3 (g)	4 (Yield%)	M.p. °C	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)		Eq. wt.	Plorate M.p. °C
				N	S		
1.	3a (4.0)	4a (74.2)	253	10.35 (10.65)	15.83 (16.25)	390.0 (394.0)	230
2.	3b HCl (4.0)	4b (65.2)	260	11.10 (11.47)	16.82 (17.47)	370.0 (336.0)	220
3.	3c HCl (4.0)	4c (52.2)	226	10.97 (10.65)	15.45 (16.25)	402.0 (394.0)	—
4.	3d (4.0)	4d (59.5)	256	10.45 (10.65)	15.85 (16.25)	391.0 (394.0)	210
5.	3e (4.0)	4e (64.2)	137	10.13 (10.65)	15.55 (16.25)	401.0 (394.0)	—

* C, H analyses satisfactory in all cases.

(725 cm⁻¹)^{2,3}, and a band due to tert-butyl group was, however, absent. On basification with dilute ammonium hydroxide it gave a free base (4a), m.p. 140°.

On the basis of all the above facts, the product with m.p. 253° has been assigned the structure as hydrobromide of 3-imino-4-*p*-tolyl-5-*p*-tolylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (4a). This de-*t*-butylation reaction was extended to others (3b–e) and the corresponding 4b–e were isolated as hydrobromides (Table 2).

When 3a was de-*t*-butylated with a boiling mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid and concentrated hydrochloric acid (1 : 3) also afforded 4^b as hydrochloride. On basification with dilute ammonium hydroxide it gave a free base, m.p. 140°. It was found identical with the free base, m.p. 140°, obtained from hydrobromide of 4a (undepressed m.m.p.).

Experimental

The 1,3-diarylthiocarbamides were prepared by the interaction of carbon disulphide and an appropriate arylamine in presence of alkali⁶. 1,3-Dibenzylthiocarbamide was prepared by heating benzylamine salt of benzylidithiocarbamic acid at 120–30°. *N*-*t*-Butyl-*S*-chloroisothiocarbamoyl chloride was prepared by the controlled chlorination of tert-butyl isothiocyanate⁷.

3-*tert*-Butylimino-4-*p*-tolyl-5-*p*-tolylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (3a): To a well cooled benzene suspension of finely powdered 2a (11.5 g or < 0.05 mol in 30 ml) was added a cold benzene solution of 1 (9.5 g in 20 ml). The temperature of the reaction mixture was maintained at 10–15°. A brisk reaction with the evolution of hydrogen chloride was noticed. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for several hours below 15°. It was then filtered to remove the unreacted 2a. The resultant filtrate on evaporation of benzene afforded a viscous liquid. It was repeatedly triturated with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) when a pale yellow solid (6 g) was isolated and crystallised from benzene, m.p. 162° (Found C, 64.86; H, 6.45; N, 10.85; S, 16.83.

C₂₀H₂₂N₂S₂ requires: C, 65.04; H, 6.23; N, 11.38; S, 17.30%.

Similarly, other 3b–e were synthesised. However, 3b and 3c were isolated as hydrochlorides and were crystallised from glacial acetic acid.

De-*t*-butylation of 3 with boiling concentrated HBr: Details of a typical experiment are as follows. When 3a (4 g) was boiled under reflux with 40 ml concentrated hydrobromic acid (47%; 40 ml) for 3 h, the compound went into solution with the evolution of *t*-butyl bromide which was detected qualitatively. The resultant reddish brown solution was cooled. The hydrobromide (4a) was isolated as a brown solid (3 g), m.p. 253° (Found: N, 10.35; S, 15.83; eq. wt. 390. C₁₆H₁₈N₂S₂HBr requires: N, 10.65; S, 16.26%; eq. wt. 394). On treatment with dilute ammonium hydroxide yielded a free base of 3-imino-4-*p*-tolyl-5-*p*-tolylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (4a), m.p. 140°.

De-*t*-butylation of 3 with boiling mixture of concentrated H₂SO₄ and HCl (1 : 3): Details of a typical experiment are as follows. 3a (4 g) was boiled with of a mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid and hydrochloric acid (1 : 3, v/v; 48 ml), under reflux for 4 h. The reaction mixture was quickly filtered and cooled, and the resulting white solid (2.5 g, hydrochloride of 4a) was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 125° (Found: N, 11.80; S, 18.03; eq. wt. 344.6. C₁₆H₁₈N₂S₂HCl requires: N, 12.01; S, 18.31%; eq. wt. 349.5). It afforded 4a, m.p. 140°, when treated with dilute ammonium hydroxide.

Acknowledgement

Two of the authors (N.K.K. and B.N.B.) are thankful to U.G.C. and C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of Teachers Fellowship and Senior Research Fellowship, respectively. Authors are thankful to Prof. K. N. Munshi, Head, Department of Chemistry for facilities.

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Terpenoids and Phenolics from the Bark and Heartwood of *Sterculia urens* Roxb.

A. S. R. ANJANEYULU* and S. NOOKA RAJU

School of Chemistry, Andhra University, Waltair-530 003

Manuscript received 30 January 1987, accepted 22 April 1987

STERCULIA urens Roxb. has been reputed for its medicinal use¹; gum in throat affections and leaves and tender branches for pleuro-pneumonia in cattle. We have reported² the isolation of a new C-methylchalcone, stercurensin from the leaves of *S. urens*. The results of the chemical examination of the bark and heartwood of *S. urens* are reported in this communication.

The air-dried and powdered bark (2 kg) of *S. urens* collected from an aged tree in the Punyagiri forests of Visakhapatnam, was extracted with methanol. The extract on concentration left β -sitosterol (Compound E, 0.2 g) which was identified by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-ir). The mother liquor after evaporation of the solvent under reduced pressure gave a residual gum (50 g) which was reextracted successively with n-hexane, chloroform and methanol. The residue (8 g) from the green hexane extract was chromatographed over a column of Si-gel to yield seven compounds: A (0.12 g, m.p. 79–80°), B (0.08 g, m.p. 107–08°), C (0.1 g, m.p. 115–16°), D (0.16 g, m.p. 204–05°), E (0.1 g, m.p. 136–37°) and F (0.1 g, m.p. 248–49°). The residue from the chloroform extract on column chromatography and elution with benzene-ethyl acetate (4:1) gave compound G (0.08 g). No crystalline compound was obtained from the methanol extract. Compounds A, B, C, D and F were identified as n-hexacosanol, cycloartenone, cycloartenol, lupeol and betulin, respectively, by comparison of their physical and spectral (ir, nmr) data and finally by direct comparison with the authentic samples (m.m.p., co-ir).

Compound G was crystallised from MeOH as brown prisms, m.p. 203–04° and analysed for $C_{10}H_8O_4$. It was recognised as a coumarin by its colour reactions³: yellow solution when heated with NaOH, and bright blue fluorescence of its methanolic solution under uv light. The ir peak at 1730 cm^{-1} and uv maxima at 342 and 294 nm further support its coumarin nature. It yielded a

monoacetate, m.p. 176–77°, and monomethyl ether, m.p. 144–50°. The characteristic 3-H and 4-H protons of coumarin appeared at δ 6.14 and 7.69 as doublets (J 9.5Hz) in its nmr spectrum in DMSO- d_6 in addition to an aromatic methoxyl at δ 3.88 and two aromatic protons as singlets at δ 6.80 and 6.98. A comparison of the above physical and spectral characteristics of compound G with those of scopoletin⁴, 7-hydroxy-6-methoxy-coumarin, proved their identity.

The air-dried and powdered heartwood of *S. urens* (5 kg) was successively extracted with n-hexane and alcohol. The residue from the hexane extract yielded 3 compounds: H (0.15 g, m.p. 84–5°), I (0.12 g, m.p. 118–20°) and J (0.1 g) in addition to cycloartenone (0.15 g), cycloartenol (0.1 g) and β -sitosterol (0.2 g) by column chromatography. The residue from the alcohol extract was further fractionated into ether and methanol solubles. The residue (35 g) obtained after evaporation of solvent from the ether extract was separated into phenolic and non-phenolic fractions by the usual treatment with basic lead acetate in methanol. The yellowish brown residue (8 g) from the phenolic fraction yielded compounds K (0.1 g), L (0.05 g) and scopoletin (0.04 g) by column chromatography.

Compounds H and I were identified as n-octacosanol and cycloartenyl acetate, respectively, by study of their physical characteristics and by direct comparison (m.m.p. and co-ir). Compound J was crystallised from $CHCl_3$ -MeOH as colourless needles, m.p. 136–37°, $[\alpha]_D +46^\circ$, $C_{30}H_{50}O$; ν_{max} 3500 (OH) and 890 cm^{-1} ($=CH_2$). It yielded a monoacetate, $C_{30}H_{52}O_2$, m.p. 150–51°, $[\alpha]_D +61.5^\circ$. The physical and spectral (ir and nmr) characteristics of compound J suggested that it might be identical with dammadienol (lit.⁵ m.p. 137°, $[\alpha]_D +47^\circ$; acetate m.p. 150–51°, $[\alpha]_D +61.5^\circ$) although a direct comparison with which could not be made.

Compound K was crystallised from MeOH as light yellow feathery needles, m.p. 206–07°, $[\alpha]_D -16.5^\circ$. It gave bright colour with Shinoda's reagent and red colour with $NaBH_4/HCl$ suggesting its flavanone nature. It was analysed for $C_{17}H_{16}O_5$, M^+ 300; showed the absorption peaks at ν_{max} (KBr) 3450 (OH) and 1640 cm^{-1} ($C=O$). A bathochromic shift of 40 nm in band II with NaOMe relative to its uv spectrum in MeOH indicated the presence of 5,7-dihydroxyl groups in K. It readily formed a diacetate, $C_{21}H_{20}O_7$, m.p. 168–70° with Ac_2O/Py and a dimethyl ether, $C_{19}H_{20}O_5$, m.p. 102° with ethereal diazomethane solution. These derivatives showed further hydroxylic ir absorption at 3250 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of 5-OH, which is supported by a D_2O -exchangeable proton at δ 11.86 in the nmr spectrum of its diacetate. With Ac_2O/CH_3COONa , compound K yielded a triacetate, $C_{23}H_{22}O_8$, m.p. 192°. The nmr spectrum of K in CD_3OD revealed the presence of characteristic flavanone protons at δ 5.25 (1H, d, J 11, 4Hz, C_8-H) and 2.80 (2H, m, C_9-2H). It further